

DYNAMIC TENSILE RESPONSE OF UNIDIRECTIONALLY-REINFORCED

CARBON EPOXY AND GLASS EPOXY COMPOSITES

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Summary

Previous work on the mechanical response of fibre-reinforced composites under impact loading is briefly reviewed and the need for testing techniques which provide data capable of a more fundamental interpretation is emphasised. Using a modified version of the split Hopkinson's bar apparatus, tensile stress-strain curves are obtained at strain rates of $\sim 10^{-4}$ /s, ~ 10 /s and $\sim 10^3$ /s for unreinforced epoxy resin specimens and for special low volume fraction model specimens unidirectionally reinforced with a single layer of glass or carbon fibre tows in the same epoxy resin. The variation of modulus, tensile strength and fracture strain with strain rate is determined and the effect of strain rate on the modes of failure examined by optical microscopy.

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Introduction

The poor impact resistance of carbon-epoxy composites and their susceptibility to microdamage under sub-critical impact loading has led to a growing awareness of the need for a full characterisation of the dynamic mechanical behaviour of such materials. Unfortunately much of the work to date on the fracture of fibre-reinforced polymeric materials under high-speed loading has employed impact bend tests where stress wave reflections and the complex modes of failure involved inhibit any fundamental analysis of the material response and of the effect of loading rate on the fracture behaviour. Both Hancox (1), in Izod impact tests on CFRP specimens, and Bader and Ellis (2), who used the Charpy impact apparatus, showed that results obtained in this way were dependent on the test-piece dimensions. Ellis and Harris (3), who tested edge-notched bend specimens of CFRP over a range of loading rates in four different testing machines, including the Charpy apparatus, found the total work of fracture, γ_f , to increase with loading rate but also concluded that their measurements of γ_f were dependent on specimen dimensions and on the type of test. Harris et al. (4) used both a miniature Charpy apparatus and a drop-weight machine to test U-notch carbon/polyester specimens but found 'difficulties in the interpretation of the data', partly because of the complexity of the crack surface topography in the impact tests.

More information can be obtained from the Charpy test when an instrumented tup is used, as was shown in a series of papers by Adams and his co-workers. They obtained load-time and energy-time records for unidirectionally-reinforced carbon, Kevlar, glass and nylon/epoxy composites (5) and observed that the total fracture energy could be closely similar for two composites despite their load-time records being very different. This led them to suggest that the peak impact load, or the energy absorbed to peak impact load, γ_i , might be a more meaningful measure of the impact resistance of the composite than the total work of fracture, γ_f . In general, however, it has not proved possible to relate data from instrumented Charpy tests to any specific micromechanisms of composite fracture, although the results obtained are not inconsistent with observations made in slow-bend tests at crosshead speeds typically of the order of 10^{-5} to 10^{-2} m/s. In such tests the fracture initiation energy, γ_i , has been associated with the rate-independent creation of new fracture surfaces and γ_f with the additional energy of fibre pull-out controlled by a rate-dependent fibre/matrix frictional interfacial stress (3,6).

Clearly, therefore, if rate effects in composite specimens under impact loading are to be related to material response at the microstructural level, simpler testing systems are required and, in particular, a uniaxial tension test (7). Early attempts to develop a high-speed tensile test for composite specimens were those of McAbee and Chmura (8), who used a pneumatically-operated loading machine and measured specimen strain by high-speed photography, obtaining failure in times as short as 7 to 10 ms, and Armenakas and Sciammarella (9), who used an explosively-propelled hammer to apply the load and high-speed photography and a moiré fringe technique to obtain the average specimen strain. A strain rate of ~ 500 /s is claimed but problems of slipping in the clamps and wave propagation effects in the 100mm long specimen were encountered. More recently, however, two techniques have been developed for the tensile impact testing of composite materials, based on the well-established Hopkinson-bar principle (10,11). The second of these has been used to obtain results for unidirectionally-reinforced CFRP, for which no effect of tensile strain rate was observed on the modulus, failure strength or fracture appearance, and also, therefore, on the work to fracture, γ_f , over some seven orders of magnitude and, in a subsequent paper (12), for woven-reinforced GFRP, where the modulus and failure strength both

increased, as did also the work of fracture, and there was a marked change in the fracture appearance. Examination of the broken specimens showed considerable matrix damage preceding final fracture in the GFRP tests but not in those on CFRP specimens. A tentative phenomenological description of failure in the woven GFRP specimens was proposed. This relates the rate-dependence of the modulus to the effect of the epoxy resin matrix resisting the straightening of the axially-aligned rovings under increasing load. The subsequent reduced stiffness ('knee effect') results from cracking in the matrix and a breakdown of the bonding between the matrix and the reinforcement while the rate dependence of both the fracture strength and the failure strain follows from the increased strength of the glass fibres at impact rates (13) allowing a greater degree of straightening before final failure. In contrast, the strain-rate independent behaviour of the CFRP specimens follows from the unidirectional nature of the reinforcement, so that the straightening mechanism no longer applies, and an apparent rate-insensitivity of the fracture strength of the carbon fibres. In these two sets of tests, however, a direct comparison between the tensile impact response of carbon and glass fibre reinforced composites was not possible because of the different reinforcement configurations in the two composites tested.

To allow such a comparison, results have been obtained more recently (14) for the strain rate sensitivity of polyester resin specimens reinforced with either carbon, glass or kevlar fibres having the same 5-end satin weave reinforcement geometry in each case. As would be expected, if the particular reinforcement geometry and resin properties were the determining factors, all three composites showed a closely similar rate dependence of the tensile modulus. A significant increase in the tensile strength of CFRP (and KFRP) specimens, however, did not support the earlier suggestion that the tensile strength of CFRP is determined solely by the rate-independent fracture strength of the carbon fibres. While the fracture appearance of CFRP and KFRP specimens was not affected by strain rate, a change in fracture mode from that controlled by the rate-dependent fracture strength of the glass at low and intermediate rates to that controlled by resistance to pull-out of fibre tows at impact rates, was observed in tests on the GFRP specimens. In early tests, undertaken during the development of the tensile impact tester, several unsuccessful attempts had been made to obtain tensile failures at impact rates in unidirectionally-reinforced GFRP specimens cut from laminates of commercial manufacture. In each case failure was by shear at the fibre-matrix interface in the grip regions of the specimen, a problem which was not encountered in subsequent tests on a fine plain-weave GFRP (12) but which reappeared in the coarser satin-weave material (14). This behaviour is likely to be related, at least in part, to the effect of strain rate on the fibre-matrix interfacial bond strength for the different reinforcement configurations.

The present paper reports on an attempt to overcome this problem by testing special model specimens of low volume fraction unidirectionally reinforced with a single layer of glass or carbon fibre tows in an epoxy resin matrix, with the aim of studying the mechanism controlling tensile failure under impact loading without the extra complications of a woven reinforcement geometry. Tests have been performed at a quasi-static, an intermediate and an impact rate, of nominally 10^{-4} , 10 and 10^3 /s, respectively, on both types of composite and on specimens of the unreinforced resin, and a preliminary examination of the fracture modes using low power optical microscopy has been undertaken.

Experimental Details

Specimen Manufacture

Specimens, to the overall dimensions previously developed for use in the impact tester (11) and shown in fig.1, were prepared from a single layer of glass or carbon fibre tows in an epoxy resin matrix using the aluminium mould shown in fig.2. This was designed to accommodate ten specimen blanks, each 9.5mm wide by 76mm long. Since it was usual to perform three tests at each of three strain rates, quasi-static, intermediate and impact, all the specimens for a given composite material could be obtained from the same casting. The carbon and glass fibres were supplied by Bristol Composite Materials Ltd. in the form of hybrid woven tape, designated Hyfil-Torayca Z tape-01 and consisting of alternate rows of continuous 600 tex E-glass rovings and Hyfil-Torayca 130-C 6000 filament fibre tows held together by a weft of glass fibre strands.

Since the width of the specimen blank was 9.5mm and the nominal width of each tow was 1.5mm, seven tows, of carbon or glass, were carefully separated from the hybrid fabric, taped together with masking tape at each end to maintain alignment, lightly stretched across the slots in the base of the mould and clamped in position using the upper side parts of the mould so that the fibres did not sag during the curing process. To ensure that the single layer of fibre tows were accurately aligned along the centre-line of the final specimen, the bottom surface of the mould was taken as a reference surface for one side of the specimen, see fig.2. The slots, within which the fibre tows are spaced, were then carefully machined to a depth which allowed the centre-line of the fibre tows to lie exactly half the total specimen thickness above the bottom of the mould. For both types of composite the calculated fibre volume fraction was $\approx 17\%$.

The resin used consisted of 100 parts by weight of Ciba-Geigy MY750, a liquid epoxy of medium viscosity, 100 parts by weight of hardener HY905 and 2 parts by weight of accelerator DY063. To wet-out the fibres a 10% solution in acetone was prepared from part of the premixed resin masterbatch. After draining off the excess solution the mould and the remaining resin masterbatch were placed in a vacuum oven at 85°C under slightly reduced pressure for 10 minutes to boil off the excess acetone. The pre-impregnated fibres were then easily wetted by the hot resin masterbatch without the formation of air pockets, after which the resin-filled mould was placed in an air-circulating fan oven, heated to 120°C and held for 4 hours. The oven was then switched off and allowed to cool to ambient temperature. A similar temperature cycle was used for the post-cure of the resin.

Testing Techniques

The impact testing technique was fully described in a paper to ICCM IV (11) and so will only be briefly described here. The specimen is fixed with epoxy adhesive into parallel-sided slots in the yoke and inertia bar and the whole assembly inserted within the weighbar tube, as shown in fig.3. A compressive impact on the upper end of the weighbar tube results in a reflected tensile stress wave loading the specimen. Strain gauges mounted on the inertia bar monitor both the stress transmitted by the specimen and the velocity of its upper end. A calibration for the velocity at the lower end of the specimen is obtained for a given impact velocity by the technique described previously

Fig.1 DESIGN OF MODEL SPECIMENS

Fig.2 MOULD DESIGN FOR MODEL SPECIMEN PREPARATION

Fig.3 Yoke IMPACT TESTER

a) Resin

b) CFRP

c) GFRP

Fig.4 INERTIA-BAR STRAIN GAUGE SIGNALS FOR IMPACT TESTS
(total sweep time - 100 μ s)

(12) and the strain determined using the standard Hopkinson-bar analysis. Signals from the inertia bar strain gauges were stored in a Data-labs type 922 transient recorder and subsequently displayed on an oscilloscope, hard copy being obtained on an X-t chart recorder. Typical oscilloscope traces for the inertia bar strain gauge signals in impact tests on the unreinforced resin and on both types of composite are shown in fig. 4, the total sweep time being 100 μ s. Comparative tests at low and intermediate rates were performed on the same design of specimen using a standard screw-driven Instron loading machine, for a strain rate of ~ 0.0001 /s, and a hydraulically-operated loading machine, for a strain rate of ~ 10 /s. In at least one test at each strain rate on each type of specimen a check of the strain in the elastic region, and hence a confirmation of the specimen modulus, was made using strain gauges attached directly to the parallel gauge region of the specimen.

Results

Stress-Strain Curves

Stress-strain curves for the unreinforced epoxy resin specimens are presented in fig. 5 for three tests at each of three strain rates, nominally 10^{-4} , 10 and 1000/s. These are average strain rates for the given test, defined as the strain at fracture divided by the time to fracture. An anomalous behaviour is apparent in the results obtained at the intermediate rate, where the stress-strain response is linear-elastic up to a strain of $\sim 2\%$ at which point a rapid unloading indicates sudden failure of the specimen. In contrast, at both the quasi-static and the impact rates the initial elastic response leads into a non-linear region and failure follows a subsequent reduction in load. In the quasi-static tests the failure strain is $\sim 4\%$ and again is indicated by a very rapid unloading. At the impact rate, however, the speed of response of the recording equipment makes it possible to follow the entire unloading process, see fig. 4a, where the unloading time is seen to be $\sim 12\mu$ s. Consequently the fracture point cannot be precisely identified. Nevertheless, previous experience with very brittle metallic specimens in the impact tester suggests that an unloading time of 12 μ s is too long for the present epoxy specimens to be failing in a similarly brittle manner and implies that the epoxy specimens are less brittle in the impact tests than in those at the intermediate rate. This raises the possibility that premature failure is occurring in tests at the intermediate rate due, perhaps, to an imperfect alignment in the hydraulically-operated loading machine used in these tests. Doubt is cast, therefore, on the validity of the measurements of maximum stress, σ_m , and fracture strain, ϵ_f , made in such tests, although estimates of the tensile modulus, E, should not be affected. Taking all the results together, however, despite some experimental scatter it is clear that there is a significant increase in tensile modulus and maximum stress but little change in the strain at fracture as the strain rate is increased from $\sim 10^{-4}$ to ~ 1000 /s.

Stress-strain curves for the CFRP specimens are presented in fig. 6 at the same three nominal strain rates. Here the tensile moduli are an order of magnitude greater than for the unreinforced resin specimens and anomalous behaviour is not observed in tests at the intermediate rate. Thus at all three strain rates fracture follows the peak load while the peak load increases and the fracture strain decreases continuously with increasing strain rate. This implies either that composite specimens are less sensitive to a small super-imposed bending stress or that their greater stiffness allows any lack of alignment when inserting the specimen to be detected more easily so that corresponding adjustments may be made. The greatest scatter is in the measurements of modulus, 39GPa \pm 8GPa, and of fracture strain, 1.05% \pm 0.26%, at the quasi-static rate. However,

Fig. 5 STRESS-STRAIN CURVES FOR UNREINFORCED RESIN SPECIMENS

Fig. 6 STRESS-STRAIN CURVES FOR CFRP SPECIMENS

Fig. 7 STRESS-STRAIN CURVES FOR GFRP SPECIMENS

taking all the CFRP results together the average fracture strain obtained here, 0.98%, is only marginally greater than the 0.90% determined in an earlier investigation (11) for a commercially obtained unidirectionally reinforced composite with a nominal volume fraction of 60%.

In tests on CFRP specimens at all strain rates only a slight departure from a linear elastic response before fracture was observed. In tests on GFRP specimens, however, see fig. 7, this type of behaviour is only shown at the quasi-static rate. At higher rates a greatly extended region of non-linear deformation is observed leading to a markedly increased value of both the maximum stress and the strain to fracture. At the intermediate rate large stress fluctuations accompany this non-linear deformation and are presumed to indicate successive bursts of damage, each occurring in a time of the order of a few hundred microseconds. As might be expected the particular response in this region differs widely from one specimen to the next, depending critically on the detailed micromechanisms of damage accumulation in each case. Overall, however, the behaviour can be described in terms of a maximum stress of $510\text{MPa} \pm 10\text{MPa}$ and a fracture strain of $6.52\% \pm 0.70\%$. Of the three specimens tested at the impact rate, one failed at a low strain, about 3.5%, following a relatively low maximum stress, about 370MPa. The other two followed the average response of the three tests at the intermediate rate, with a similar maximum stress of $494 \pm 16\text{MPa}$ and fracture strain of $6.7 \pm 0.5\%$ but without the large stress fluctuations. Since the total duration of the test is less than $100\mu\text{s}$ the absence of stress fluctuations is, perhaps, not surprising. It does imply, however, a change in the micromechanics of fracture.

Fracture Appearance

At all rates of strain both the unreinforced epoxy and the CFRP composite specimens failed in a brittle manner. Failure in the CFRP specimens was characterised by a very small fibre pull-out length and no sign of fibre debonding. Some specimens failed at a single cross-section, see fig. 8a, others at two, fig. 8b, or more, fig. 8c, cross-sections, showing irregular matrix cracks both longitudinal and transverse to the fibres. The longitudinal splitting is probably associated with a plane of weakness or resin-rich zone between individual fibre tows due to slight differences in specimen preparation and illustrating the sensitivity of the mechanical response to these differences. The various types of fracture appearance shown in fig. 8 were typical of CFRP specimens at all rates of loading.

A significantly different fracture behaviour was shown by the GFRP specimens. At the quasi-static rate, where the stress-strain response was essentially linear elastic to failure, all specimens fractured suddenly with no signs of damage before fracture but with a great deal of damage apparent, see fig. 9a, after failure. In particular, there is evidence of extensive matrix cracking and fibre debonding with long lengths of fibres pulled out of the matrix on either side of the fracture surface. A generally similar fracture appearance was obtained at the intermediate rate, see fig. 9b, except that the damage here was more extensive, as might be expected from the corresponding stress-strain curves, and the specimen shattered on fracture to give the debris of broken fibres and pieces of matrix also shown in fig. 9b. The fibre pull-out lengths were very long and the debonded zones extended into the grip region at one end of the specimen. At the impact rate, a change in the mode of fracture of the GFRP specimens was observed. Instead of a tensile failure in the gauge section of the specimen the glass fibres pulled out of the matrix in one of the grip regions, see fig. 9c, implying

(a) Single fracture surface (b) Stepped fracture surface
 transverse cracking (c) Multi-stepped fracture surface,
 transverse and longitudinal cracking

Fig.8 FRACTURE APPEARANCE OF CFRP SPECIMENS (x3.5)

that at this loading rate the fibre-matrix interfacial bond strength was exceeded before the tensile failure strength of the composite was attained. Since the maximum stress supported by the specimens was similar in tests at both intermediate and impact rates, this suggests that the tensile strength of the E-glass fibres increases with strain rate, in agreement with the conclusions of earlier studies (12,13,14). Examination of the gauge section of a specimen which had previously failed by fibre pull-out in the grip region reveals under transmitted light, fig. 9d, the presence of many matrix cracks, and under reflected light, fig. 9e, the debonding of fibres over a short distance to either side of these matrix cracks. Clearly, in the glass-reinforced composites, matrix cracking may precede failure and its presence does not necessarily precipitate fracture of the fibres.

Discussion

Because of the difficulty of obtaining tensile failures in unidirectionally reinforced glass fibre composites all previous studies at Oxford of the tensile impact response of GFRP have been concerned with woven reinforcement geometries. By using model specimens in the present investigation, with a low volume fraction of reinforcing fibres, it had been hoped to overcome this problem. However, as is clearly apparent from fig. 9c, which shows behaviour typical of the GFRP specimens under impact loading, this aim was not achieved. It had also been hoped that the use of a unidirectional reinforcement geometry would simplify the interpretation of the experimental results in comparison with the more complex resin/reinforcement interaction encountered in woven reinforced specimens. However, in view of the difficulty of obtaining repeatable results from such small laboratory-prepared specimens, illustrated, for example, in the impact stress-strain curves for GFRP in fig. 7, it is clear that the relatively few tests reported on here are insufficient to allow any firm conclusions to be drawn. Nevertheless the trends in mechanical response observed do follow those obtained in earlier work and may be discussed in relation to that work.

a) Quasi-static test (x2.2)

b) Intermediate rate test (x2.4)

c

d

e

Impact test: c) pull-out of fibre layer in grip region (x2.0)
 d) unbroken gauge section viewed by transmitted light showing matrix cracks (x2.8)
 e) unbroken gauge section viewed by reflected light showing debonding around cracks (x2.6)

Fig.9 EFFECT OF STRAIN RATE ON FRACTURE APPEARANCE OF GFRP SPECIMENS

Effect of Strain Rate on the Tensile (Youngs) Modulus

The variation of Youngs modulus with strain rate for the unreinforced resin and the two types of composite is shown in fig.10. As discussed elsewhere (11,12) the experimental accuracy with which the modulus can be determined in the impact tests is estimated to be about $\pm 5\%$. The scatter in the quasi-static modulus measurements for the present CFRP tests is much greater than this, about $\pm 20\%$. Nevertheless, the results of fig.10 show, for both composites, a clearly marked increase in modulus between the intermediate and the impact loading rate, by about 20% for the CFRP and

30% for the GFRP specimens. Similar, if rather greater, increases have been observed previously in woven-reinforced CFRP and GFRP (12,14) where an explanation was proposed in terms of a strong interaction between the matrix and the reinforcement as the axially-aligned rovings straightened under the applied tensile loading. In the present tests a straightening mechanism of this type cannot apply so the only effect of the matrix is directly through the rate dependence of its modulus, E_r . Using a simple rule of mixtures approach, the composite modulus is given by

$$E_C = E_f V_f + E_r (1 - V_f). \quad (1)$$

Taking a volume fraction of 17%, resin modulus values from fig.10 and rate independent fibre moduli of 230GPa, for carbon fibres, and 72GPa, for E-glass fibres, equation (1) gives the predicted strain-rate dependence shown in fig.10 for the moduli of the two composites. Although the discrepancy between prediction and experiment at low and intermediate rates is not unreasonable, for neither composite does the predicted response show the experimentally observed rate dependence at the impact loading rate. A possible source of error arises from the determination of modulus by the use of strain gauges attached to the surface of low volume fraction specimens in which the reinforcing fibres are concentrated around the central plane. This could well result in the strain gauges overestimating the mean strain in the specimen and lead to an underestimate of the composite modulus as defined in equation (1) which is itself not directly applicable to specimens of this type. The effect will, of course, be present at all strain rates. Assuming a rate dependent shear modulus for the resin, related to E_r by a Poisson's ratio of 0.3, approximate calculations suggest that, for CFRP specimens, the corrected moduli will exceed those shown in fig.10 by about 5% and will show a slightly increased rate sensitivity at the impact loading rates while, for GFRP specimens, the increase in modulus will be ~3% and the rate sensitivity will be unchanged. It seems clear, therefore, that the rate sensitivity of the modulus in fibre-reinforced plastics cannot be explained solely in terms of the rate dependence of the resin modulus measured in isolation.

Effect of Strain Rate on the Tensile Strength

The variation of tensile strength with strain rate for the unreinforced resin and the two types of composite is shown in fig.11. In previous work on high volume fraction ($V_f = 60\%$) unidirectionally-reinforced CFRP (11) the tensile strength was completely independent of strain rate over the entire range from 10^{-4} to $10^3/s$, implying that the rate independent fracture strength of the carbon fibres was the controlling factor in the failure of the composite. However, in later tests on CFRP with a satin-weave reinforcement geometry (14) a significant increase in the failure strength was observed, by about 30%, as the strain rate was increased from ~10/s to ~700/s, although below 10/s no significant rate dependence was observed. Again the strong interaction between the woven reinforcement and the rate-dependent resin as the axially-aligned rovings straighten under tensile loading was proposed to explain the increased strength of the composite at high strain rates. In the present tests on CFRP specimens, see fig.11, a similar behaviour to that shown by the satin-weave CFRP specimens was obtained. The tensile strength was almost independent of strain rate at rates below ~10/s but then increased, by about 15%, a margin slightly greater than the scatter band at each strain rate, as the strain rate was raised to ~350/s. Because of the unidirectional nature of the reinforcement the resin/re-

Fig.10
STRAIN-RATE DEPENDENCE OF TENSILE MODULUS

Fig.11
STRAIN-RATE DEPENDENCE OF TENSILE STRENGTH

Fig.12
STRAIN-RATE DEPENDENCE OF FRACTURE STRAIN

inforcement interaction is likely to be significantly less in these tests than in those on the satin-weave specimens. The above explanation is even less convincing, therefore, in this case. In the present tests, however, an approximate check on the contribution of the resin is possible, in terms of the simple rule of mixtures prediction of the composite strength, σ_c . This gives

$$\sigma_c = \sigma_f V_f + E_r (1 - V_f) / 100, \quad (2)$$

where σ_f is the tensile strength of the carbon fibres, taken to be 2.4GPa at all strain rates, and E_r is the resin modulus, which varies with strain rate as shown in fig.10. Since all CFRP specimens failed at a strain close to 1%, see fig.12, the tensile stress in the resin at composite failure is taken to be $E_r/100$. Predicted composite failure strengths from equation (2) are shown in fig.11. They exceed the experimentally measured failure strengths by about 20% and, unlike the experimental results, show

no significant strain-rate dependence at strain rates above 10/s. As with the modulus, therefore, it seems that the rate sensitivity of the tensile strength in CFRP specimens cannot be explained solely in terms of the effect of the resin.

No previous results have been obtained by the present authors on unidirectionally-reinforced GFRP. However, both plain-weave (12) and satin-weave (14) GFRP specimens have been tested at the same three nominal strain rates as used here and both showed the same marked increase in tensile strength between the quasi-static and the intermediate rate tests, by $\sim 70\%$ for the plain weave and $\sim 50\%$ for the satin-weave specimens. In both cases the strain to fracture also increased, from $\sim 1.8\%$ to $\sim 2.7\%$ for the plain-weave and from $\sim 3\%$ to $\sim 6.5\%$ for the satin-weave specimens. At the intermediate rate a reduced stiffness, sometimes described as a 'knee effect', was observed in both woven composites but was more clearly marked in the satin-weave specimens. This reduced stiffness, and the corresponding increase in strain to fracture, were explained in terms of a breakdown of the bonding between resin and reinforcement, giving the reduced stiffness, and an increased fibre strength at high rates (13), allowing greater straightening of the fibres and hence increased overall extension before fibre fractures lead to general failure.

In the present tests on unidirectionally-reinforced GFRP generally similar behaviour is observed. The tensile strength increases by about 40%, from $\sim 340\text{MPa}$ at $10^{-4}/\text{s}$ to $\sim 510\text{MPa}$ at $\sim 20/\text{s}$ while the fracture strain shows a corresponding increase, see fig. 12, from $\sim 2.6\%$ to $\sim 6.2\%$. This increase in fracture strain is of the same order as that shown by the satin-weave specimens but without any fibre-straightening mechanism to provide the extension. For the plain-weave specimens, however, where the reinforcement geometry would be expected to give the largest extension from fibre straightening (approximately 2.5 x that for a 5-end satin-weave construction) the measured fracture strains were the smallest and the least rate sensitive. Clearly, therefore, both for the previous satin-weave specimens and in the present GFRP tests an alternative deformation mechanism must make the major contribution to the large failure strains obtained in the intermediate rate tests. That this mechanism is the pull-out of fibre tows is clear from fig. 9. At the quasi-static rate, fig. 9a, some fibre pull-out is observed either side of a tensile fracture surface which crosses the gauge section of the specimen at two positions joined by a single step parallel to the fibres. At the intermediate rate, fig. 9b, fibre pull-out is much more extensive and the fracture surfaces are less easily discerned. However, the increased failure strength at the intermediate rate supports the conclusion that here also failure is controlled by the tensile fracture strength of the glass fibres. In the impact tests, however, a reduced fracture strength is observed, see fig. 11, accompanied by a complete change in the mode of failure, see fig. 9c, so that pull-out of fibres, rather than fibre fracture, becomes the controlling process. A similar observation was made in the impact tests on the satin-weave, but not the plain-weave, specimens lending further support to the earlier suggestion (14) that debonding between glass fibre tows and the resin matrix becomes easier with increasing strain rate.

Conclusions

Tensile stress-strain curves have been obtained at strain rates of $\sim 10^{-4}$, $\sim 10^3$ and $\sim 10^3/\text{s}$ for unreinforced epoxy resin specimens and for special low volume fraction model specimens unidirectionally-reinforced with a single layer of glass or carbon fibre tows in the same epoxy resin. For CFRP specimens a small rate dependence of both the modulus and the tensile strength was observed at impact rates of strain.

This effect is greater than can be explained in terms of the rate sensitivity of the resin using the rule of mixtures approach. As in previous tests on both woven and unidirectionally-reinforced CFRP no effect of strain rate on the fracture appearance could be detected. In contrast, there was a marked change in the fracture mode of GFRP specimens, similar to that previously reported for a satin-weave GFRP material. At low and intermediate rates failure was controlled by the rate-dependent fracture strength of the glass fibres while, at impact rates, pull-out of fibre tows became the controlling mechanism. This supports a previous suggestion that there is a greater tendency for debonding between the fibre tows and the resin matrix at impact rates of strain.

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References

1. N. L. Hancox, "Izod impact testing of carbon-fibre-reinforced plastics", Composites, (1) (1971) pp. 41-45
2. M. G. Bader and R. M. Ellis, "The effect of notches and specimen geometry on the pendulum impact strength of uniaxial cfrp", Composites, (4) (1974) pp. 253-258
3. C. D. Ellis and B. Harris, "The Effect of Specimen and Testing Variables on the Fracture of some Fibre Reinforced Epoxy Resins", J. Comp. Materials, (7) (1973) pp. 76-88
4. B. Harris, P. W. R. Beaumont and E. Moncunill de Ferran, "Strength and Fracture Toughness of Carbon Fibre Polyester Composites", J. Mat. Sci., (6) (1971) pp. 238-251
5. Donald F. Adams and John L. Perry, "Instrumented Charpy Impact Tests of several Unidirectional Composite Materials", Fibre Science and Technology, (8) (1975) pp. 275-302
6. Gad Marom, Nili Konieczny and Floyd R. Tuler, "Time-dependent fracture in a unidirectional glass fibre-reinforced epoxy material", J. Mat. Sci. Letters, (11) (1976) pp. 1974-1977
7. Donald F. Adams, "Impact Response of Polymer-Matrix Composite Materials", Composite Materials: Testing and Design (Fourth Conference), ASTM STP 617, American Society for Testing and Materials (1977) pp. 409-426
8. Elise McAbee and Mitchel Chmura, "Effects of High Rates compared with Static Rates of Loading on the Mechanical Properties of Glass Reinforced Plastics", Proc. 16th. Annual Tech. Conf., SPI Reinforced Plastics Division, Chicago (Society of Plastics Industry, New York) (1961) paper 13-D
9. A. E. Armenakas and C. A. Sciammarella, "Response of Glass-fiber-reinforced Epoxy Specimens to High Rates of Tensile Loading", Experimental Mechanics, (13) (1973) pp. 433-440
10. K. Kawata, A. Hondo, S. Hashimoto, N. Takeda and H. L. Chung, "Dynamic behaviour analysis of composite materials", Proc. Japan - U.S. Conference on Composite Materials, ed. K. Kawata and T. Akasaka (Japan Society for Composite Materials, Tokyo) (1981) pp. 2-11
11. J. Harding and L. M. Welsh, "Impact testing of fibre reinforced composite materials", Proc. 4th. Int. Conf. on Composite Materials (Japan Soc. for Composite Materials, Tokyo) (1) (1982) pp. 845-852

12. J. Harding and L. M. Welsh, "A tensile testing technique for fibre-reinforced composites at impact rates of strain", J. Mat. Sci., (18) (1983) pp. 1810-1826
13. A. Rotem and J. M. Lifshitz, "Longitudinal strength of unidirectional fibrous composite under high rate of loading", Proc. 26th. Annual Tech. Conf., SPI Reinforced Plastics/Composites Division (Society of PLastics Industry, New York) (1971) paper 10-G
14. L. M. Welsh and J. Harding, "Effect of strain rate on the tensile failure of woven-reinforced polyester resin composites", to be presented at DYMAT 85, Int. Conf. on Mech. and Physical Behaviour of Materials under Dynamic Loading, ECTA, Paris, September 1985

